

Current Concepts in Temporomandibular Joint Dysfunction Associated With Occlusal Disorders: A Systematic Review

Authors:

Oleksandr Belikov, Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Professor of the Department of Prosthetic Dentistry - ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8828-6311>

Oleksandra Roshchuk, Candidate of Medical Sciences, Head of the Department of Prosthetic Dentistry - ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1877-1546>

Nataliia Belikova, Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Prosthetic Dentistry - ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2304-2089>

Mykola Sorokhan, Candidate of Medical Sciences, Lecture of the Department of Prosthetic Dentistry - ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7331-6298>

Yaroslav Karavan, Candidate of Medical Sciences, Lecture of the Department of Prosthetic Dentistry - ORCID: : <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5111-2462>

Affiliations:

Bukovinian State Medical University, Ministry of Health of Ukraine, Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Corresponding Author:

Oleksandr Belikov

E-mail: belikovsasha@ukr.net

Mobile: +38 (050) 196-93-00

Preprint Notice: This manuscript is a preprint and has not undergone peer review. It is shared to support early dissemination of scientific findings and may contain updates in future versions.

License: Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY-4.0)

1. ABSTRACT

2. **Background.** Temporomandibular joint dysfunction (TMD) remains an актуальным problem of modern dentistry, as disturbances of occlusion and masticatory muscle function lead to structural changes in the joint, development of pain syndrome and functional limitations. **Purpose** - to systematize and analyze scientific data on the role of occlusal interferences in the development of temporomandibular joint dysfunction by summarizing pathogenetic mechanisms, diagnostic criteria, and modern treatment approaches. **Materials and Methods** - a systematic analysis of scientific publications from 2015 to 2025 was performed using the databases PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar databases following PRISMA guidelines. Terming MeSH included: “temporomandibular joint dysfunction”, “occlusal interference”, “mandibular deviation”, “bruxism”, “occlusal adjustment”, “CBCT”, “electromyography”, applying the logical operators AND, OR, NOT, **Results** - the clinical course of the disorder is also influenced by mandibular fractures, orthodontic anomalies, prosthetic errors, periodontal diseases, bruxism and psycho-emotional stress. For early diagnosis, a complex approach using clinical, radiological and functional methods is recommended, including cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), electromyography, axiography, and digital occlusal analysis (T-Scan). Special emphasis is placed on the application of standardized diagnostic criteria (DC/TMD and RDC/TMD) and validated questionnaires for the assessment of pain intensity and functional limitations. Effective treatment should be comprehensive and include elimination of pathological occlusal contacts, splint therapy, physiotherapy, correction of parafunctions and psycho-emotional conditions, and, in cases of severe morphological changes, prosthetic and surgical interventions. **Conclusions** - according to recent meta-analyses, the use of stabilization and repositioning splints provides clinical improvement in 70–85% of patients. The obtained findings have significant practical value for improving the diagnosis, prevention, treatment and rehabilitation of patients with occlusal disturbances associated with temporomandibular joint dysfunction. The results also emphasize the

necessity of a multidisciplinary approach using modern digital technologies in clinical practice.

3. Keywords: diagnostics; occlusal correction; dental occlusion; temporomandibular disorders; splint therapy

4. Introduction.

5. Temporomandibular joint (TMJ) dysfunction is a multifactorial pathology that combines functional, muscular, structural and psycho-emotional components.

6. According to epidemiological studies, symptoms of TMJ dysfunction are observed in 20-40% of the adult population, whereas clinically significant manifestations occur in approximately 10% of patients [1]. Among the factors contributing to the development of this syndrome, a significant role is played by occlusal interferences – premature or pathological contacts between teeth that cause asymmetry of masticatory loading, changes in the position of the mandible and compensatory hyperactivity of the masticatory muscles, leading to overload of TMJ structures [2-4].

7. Clinical studies demonstrate that patients with occlusal interferences have a higher prevalence of pain symptoms, joint sounds and limitation of mouth opening compared to individuals with physiological occlusion [5].

8. Despite active discussion regarding the role of occlusion in the pathogenesis of TMJ dysfunction, most contemporary authors agree that occlusal interferences are an important, though not the only, factor in the development of this pathology [3, 6, 7].

9. Thus, systematization of current concepts concerning the etiological and pathogenetic role of occlusal interferences in the development of TMJ dysfunction is a relevant task of clinical dentistry.

10. Materials and methods.

11. The object of the study comprised scientific publications devoted to temporomandibular joint dysfunction in patients with occlusal interferences. A systematic literature search was performed in the international scientometric databases PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar for the period 2015-2025.

12. The search strategy was based on the use of the following English keywords and

their combinations: “temporomandibular joint dysfunction”, “occlusal interference”, “mandibular deviation”, “bruxism”, “occlusal adjustment”, “CBCT”, “electromyography”. To refine and improve the relevance of the results, the logical operators AND, OR and NOT were applied.

- 13.** The analysis included: full-text scientific articles, original clinical studies, systematic reviews and meta-analyses published in English or Ukrainian in peer-reviewed journals.
- 14.** Additionally, the ResearchGate platform was screened to identify preprints and full-text articles in PDF format.
- 15.** The selection of sources was carried out according to PRISMA principles and included the following stages [8]. The literature search initially identified 200 records across PubMed, Scopus and Google Scholar databases. After removing duplicates and screening titles and abstracts, 150 records remained. Following full-text assessment, 100 articles were evaluated for eligibility. Ultimately, 30 studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the qualitative synthesis.
- 16.** The flowchart for selecting publications according to the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses) 2020 recommendations is formed and depicted in Figure 1. Bibliographic and analytical methods were used to prepare and design the manuscript.

17. **Figure 1.** PRISMA 2020 Flow diagram of study selection reporting guidelines for systematic reviews and meta-analyses [8]

18. Results

- 19.** An analysis of current scientific of TMJ dysfunction as sociated with occlusal interference.
- 20.** 1. Definition and classification of TMJ dysfunction as sociated with occlusal interference.
- 21.** Temporomandibular joint dysfunction associated with occlusal interference is defined as a complex of functional, morphological and occluso-muscular disorders caused by pathological contacts between opposing teeth, which disturb the coordination between mandibular position, masticatory muscle activity and joint structures [3, 4, 6].
- 22.** According to current concepts, occlusal interferences lead to chronic overload of one or both condylar heads, impaired interaction of the articular disc with the condylar processes and asymmetry of neuromuscular activity of the masticatory muscles, thereby contributing to the development of clinical manifestations of TMJ dysfunction [2, 5, 7].
- 23.** According to generally accepted classifications, TMJ dysfunction is divided into the following main forms:
- 24.** • Muscular (myogenic) – characterized by predominant pain in the masticatory muscles without pronounced morphological changes in the joint structures;
- 25.** • Intra-articular – associated with displacement of the articular disc (with or without reduction);
- 26.** • Combined – a combination of muscular and intra-articular disorders [3, 10, 11].
- 27.** In addition, according to the course, acute (up to 3 months), subacute (3-6 months) and chronic forms (more than 6 months) are distinguished, which has prognostic significance for the choice of treatment tactics [10, 11]. Current studies also propose to consider TMJ dys function as part of a multifactorial orofacial pain syn drome, taking into account the role of biomechanical, psycho-emotional and occlusal factors [6, 7, 12].

- 28.** 2. Pathogenesis of TMJ dysfunction associated with occlusal interference.
- 29.** The pathogenesis of temporomandibular joint dysfunction in the presence of occlusal interferences is based on disruption of functional balance within the “dental arches – masticatory muscles – TMJ” system, which leads to chronic overload of joint and muscular structures [13-15].
- 30.** Premature occlusal contacts alter the physiological trajectory of mandibular movement, causing its forced displacement in the sagittal, transverse or frontal planes. In response, asymmetrical activity of the masticatory muscles, particularly the lateral pterygoid and temporal muscles, develops, resulting in their prolonged hyperactivity and the development of myofascial pain syndrome [14, 16].
- 31.** Further progression of the process includes several pathogenetic stages: mechanical destabilization of the joint, premature contacts induces uneven load distribution on the articular surfaces, leading to microtrauma of cartilage and disc [13, 17], muscle dysfunction and spasm.
- 32.** Chronic asymmetry of muscle activity is accompanied by the formation of trigger zones, restriction of mandibular movements and intensification of pain manifestations [14, 18].
- 33.** Articular disc displacement. Under conditions of prolonged overload, anterior disc displacement with or without reduction develops, which is clinically manifested by clicking, episodes of locking and limitation of mouth opening [16, 19].
- 34.** Degenerative changes in joint structures. Prolonged pathological loading initiates remodeling of bone structures, development of osteophytes, erosions, subchondral sclerosis and fibrotic changes in the capsular-ligamentous apparatus of the joint [17, 20].
- 35.** Occlusal interferences also contribute to the formation of a closed pathological circle in which muscular dysfunction, changes in disc position and degenerative TMJ lesions mutually potentiate one another [13, 15].
- 36.** Modern biomechanical models demonstrate that even minor disturbances in occlusal balance can cause significant changes in load distribution on the

articular surfaces, increasing the risk of chronicity of the process [21].

37. 3. Methods of early diagnosis.
38. Comprehensive diagnosis of temporomandibular joint dysfunction should include clinical, instrumental, functional and imaging methods that make it possible to assess both the functional state of the joint and morphological changes in its structures [22].
39. Clinical methods. Clinical examination includes: palpation of the masticatory muscles and TMJ, assessment of the range and symmetry of mouth opening, detection of mandibular deviation or deflection during opening, analysis of clicking, crepitation and tenderness in the joint area.
40. Occlusal analysis is also performed using articulating paper, foil and functional clinical tests [23, 24].
41. To obtain a standardized assessment of the condition of patients with TMJ dysfunction, the following are used: DC/TMD (Diagnostic Criteria for Temporomandibular Disorders), Helkimo Index, Fonseca Anamnestic Index, Visual Analog Scale (VAS), Jaw Functional Limitation Scale (JFLS), which serve as validated clinical tools for evaluating pain and functional limitations [10, 11, 25].
42. Radiological methods. Imaging methods are crucial for detecting morphological joint changes:
43. • Cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) allows assessment of the condition of bony joint structures, the presence of erosions, osteophytes, sclerosis and flattening of articular surfaces [26].
44. • Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is considered the “gold standard” for the visualization of the articular disc, inflammatory changes and soft tissue components of the joint [27, 28].
45. • Orthopantomography is used as an auxiliary screening method, particularly at the initial stages of examination [29].
46. Functional and digital methods. To objectively assess the functional state of the musculo-articular complex, the following are used:
47. • Electromyography (EMG) – to evaluate symmetry and intensity of

masticatory muscle activity [29];

48. • Axioigraphy / kinesiography – to record mandibular movement trajectories and detect functional movement disorders in the TMJ [30];
49. • Digital occlusal analysis (T-Scan) – to quantitatively assess the force, timing and uniformity of occlusal contacts [30].
50. Comprehensive application of these methods allows not only detection of TMJ dysfunction, but also the establishment of a causal relationship between occlusal interferences, functional changes and structural alternations in the joint [22, 28, 29].
51. 4. Morphological changes in TMJ dysfunction.
52. According to modern imaging methods (CBCT, MRI), patients with TMJ dysfunction associated with occlusal interferences present a complex of characteristic morphological changes involving both bony and soft-tissue joint structures [26-28].
53. The main changes in the bony structures include: erosions and flattening of the condylar head, formation of marginal osteophytes, subchondral sclerosis, remodeling of articular surface contours [17, 20, 26].
54. The most common changes in the articular disc are: anterior or anteromedial displacement with or without reduction, deformation of disc shape, fibrotic changes and local degenerative lesions [27, 28, 30].
55. Changes in the capsular-ligamentous apparatus manifestas: capsular fibrosis, reduced elasticity, disturbed disc stabilization during mandibular movements [19, 27].
56. In the masticatory muscles, the following are noted: hypertonus, asymmetry of contractions, formation of myofascial trigger zones, local dystrophic changes [14, 30].
57. Thus, morphological disorders form a persistent functional-structural imbalance within the “dental arches – muscles – TMJ” system, which maintains and promotes progression of clinical symptoms.
58. 5. Functional disorders.
59. The main clinical manifestations include: limitation of mouth opening

(<35mm), deviation or deviation with shift during opening, clicking, crepitation or “locking” (in the presence of disc displacement), pain in the TMJ area, masticatory muscles and cervical region, midline shift, appearance of premature contacts and changes in occlusal relationships [3, 5, 24, 25].

- 60.** The severity of symptoms correlates with the type and duration of occlusal interferences and the presence of concomitant risk factors (bruxism, stress, orthodontic anomalies) [11, 14, 19, 20, 28, 30].
- 61.** 6. Risk factors for the development of TMJ dysfunction associated with occlusal interferences.
- 62.** Risk factors for TMJ dysfunction are multifactorial and can be conditionally divided into mechanical, functional, biological, psycho-emotional and individual [12].
- 63.** Mechanical factors: presence of occlusal interferences, errors in prosthetic treatment, orthodontic anomalies, consequences of mandibular fractures [2, 5, 30].
- 64.** Functional factors: bruxism, unilateral chewing, chronic parafunctions of the masticatory muscles [14, 22].
- 65.** Biological factors: rheumatic and degenerative diseases, inflammatory processes in the joint, periodontal lesions, hormonal changes [20, 26].
- 66.** Psycho-emotional factors: chronic stress, anxiety and depressive disorders are statistically associated with the development and chronicity of pain syndrome in TMJ dysfunction [12, 14].
- 67.** Individual factors: female sex, age 20-45 years, anatomical features of articular surfaces, hereditary predisposition [5, 7].
- 68.** The combined effect of several risk factors not only increases the likelihood of TMJ dysfunction, but also leads to a more severe and chronic course of the disease [11, 12].
- 69.** 7. Prognostic markers.
- 70.** Clinical markers.
- 71.** An unfavorable prognosis of TMJ dysfunction is associated with the following clinical features: pain duration longer than 3 months, frequent episodes of

mandibular locking, significant limitation of mouth opening (<30-35 mm), pronounced asymmetry of mandibular movements, combination of muscular and intra-articular components of dysfunction.

- 72.** These signs are associated with a high risk of chronicity and poorer response to standard therapy [10, 15, 25, 27].
- 73.** Instrumental markers.
- 74.** Unfavorable instrumental prognostic features include: disc displacement without reduction according to MRI, erosive changes, osteophytes and condylar remodeling according to CBCT, asymmetry of EMG activity of the masticatory muscles, disturbed mandibular movement trajectories according to axiography.
- 75.** These parameters are associated with progression of degenerative joint changes and lower effectiveness of conservative therapy [7, 19, 21, 23, 27].
- 76.** Biochemical markers.
- 77.** Studies have shown that patients with a severe course of TMJ dysfunction exhibit: increased levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL1 β , TNF- α), increased activity of matrix metalloproteinases (in particular MMP-9), enhanced local inflammatory response in synovial fluid.
- 78.** These changes are associated with progression of degenerative processes in the TMJ [26, 10].
- 79.** Psycho-emotional and behavioral markers.
- 80.** Unfavorable prognostic factors also include: high levels of psycho-emotional stress, pronounced bruxism, concomitant anxiety and depressive disorders.
- 81.** These factors significantly increase the risk of pain chronicity and development of treatment-resistant forms of TMJ dysfunction [14, 29].
- 82.** 8. Treatment outcomes and rehabilitation.
- 83.** The effectiveness of treatment of temporomandibular joint dysfunction largely depends on etiological factors, disease stage, the presence of morphological changes and adequacy of the chosen therapeutic strategy.
- 84.** Modern evidence-based approaches confirm the advisability of a multidisciplinary treatment strategy combining dental, functional,

physiotherapeutic and psychotherapeutic methods [3, 15, 25].

- 85.** Conservative treatment.
- 86.** The main goals of conservative therapy are: pain reduction, normalization of musculo-articular function, stabilization of mandibular position, elimination of pathogenic occlusal interferences [33].
- 87.** Occlusal correction.
- 88.** Selective grinding, correction of restorations and reorganization of occlusal relationships help reduce pathological loading on the joint and stabilize the functional state of the system [3, 24].
- 89.** Splint therapy.
- 90.** Stabilization and repositioning splints contribute to: reduction of pain, normalization of muscle activity, improvement of mandibular range of motion.
- 91.** According to systematic reviews, clinical improvement is observed in 70-85% of patients [8, 12, 29].
- 92.** Physiotherapy and rehabilitation.
- 93.** The main physiotherapeutic methods include: transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), kinesiotherapy, therapeutic exercises for the masticatory muscles, manual and myofascial techniques.
- 94.** Combination of physiotherapy with occlusal splint therapy shows significantly better results in terms of pain reduction and improvement of TMJ function [12, 24, 29].
- 95.** Pharmacotherapy.
- 96.** Pharmacological treatment includes: non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, muscle relaxants, in resistant cases – intra-articular injections of hyaluronic acid or corticosteroids.
- 97.** Systematic reviews confirm the effectiveness of intra-articular injections in reducing pain and improving joint mobility [10, 15, 26].
- 98.** Orthopedic and surgical rehabilitation.
- 99.** In patients with severe structural changes or treatment-resistant forms of the disease, the following are used: orthopedic restoration of occlusion

(prosthetics, orthodontic correction), minimally invasive surgical interventions (arthrocentesis, arthroscopy), in selected cases – open surgery.

100. The effectiveness of such interventions has been demonstrated in studies on patients with post-traumatic and degenerative TMJ dysfunction [15, 26, 30].

101. Long-term outcomes.

102. According to clinical observations, most patients with functional forms of TMJ dysfunction demonstrate stable improvement when staged and individualized treatment is followed [8, 24, 25, 29, 30].

103. At the same time, in patients with pronounced degenerative joint changes, the course of the disease may be recurrent, requiring long-term follow-up and therapeutic adjustments [15, 26].

104. Discussion

105. The results obtained are consistent with contemporary systematic reviews and clinical studies that confirm the leading role of occlusal interferences in the pathogenesis of TMJ dysfunction [1, 3, 6, 28, 30]. Premature occlusal contacts disrupt the biomechanical balance between the dental arches, muscles and joint, leading to increased loading on the articular disc and the development of inflammatory-degenerative changes [5-7, 10, 18, 27].

106. Data from numerous studies demonstrate the diagnostic value of CBCT, which allows for the detection of early morphological changes in joints [16,20]. The role of MRI in the diagnosis of internal TMJ derangements has been confirmed by studies [17, 27]. This is consistent with our generalized conclusions regarding the feasibility of combining functional (EMG, T-Scan, axiography) and morphological diagnostics [18, 23, 28, 29].

107. With regard to treatment, the results of the review confirm the effectiveness of a multidisciplinary approach combining occlusal correction with splint therapy, physiotherapy, and control of psychoemotional factors [9, 14, 24-26, 29, 30]. According to Wang L. et al. [7], the effectiveness of splint therapy reaches 80-85%, which is consistent with clinical observations in patients after mandibular fractures [30].

108. Similar conclusions are presented in studies where TMJ dysfunction is

considered part of complex facial pain syndromes that require a multidisciplinary approach involving dentists, neurologists, psychologists and physical rehabilitation specialists [5, 24, 25].

109. Thus, the systematic analysis performed confirms that occlusal interferences are a key, but not the only, etiological factor in the development of TMJ dysfunction. Effective treatment requires integration of dental, orthopedic, neurological and rehabilitation methods using modern digital technologies for occlusal assessment.

110. Similar conclusions regarding the role of occlusal interferences in temporomandibular joint dysfunction have also been reported in recent systematic reviews [31].

111. Despite the systematic approach and the use of several databases, the study has a number of limitations: language limitations: only articles in English and Ukrainian were included, which may have resulted in omission of relevant publications in other languages.

112. Lack of quantitative meta-analysis: due to heterogeneity of study designs (clinical, experimental, review), the results were summarized in a descriptive format.

113. Differences in diagnostic criteria: the included studies used different protocols (RDC/TMD, DC/TMD, authors' own schemes), which complicates direct comparison of results [16, 27, 28].

114. Potential publication bias: a predominance of positive results in published sources may affect the objectivity of generalizations.

115. Conclusions.

116. 1. Occlusal interferences are important etiological factors in the development of temporomandibular joint disorders (TMD), promoting disturbance of mandibular biomechanics, the formation of muscular asymmetry and progressive degeneration of joint structures.

117. 2. Additional factors such as mandibular fractures, orthodontic anomalies, errors in prosthetic treatment, periodontal diseases and inadequate dental restorations may disrupt the functional balance within the dento-muscular-

articular system and contribute to the development or progression of TMJ dysfunction.

118. 3. Comprehensive diagnostic approaches including electromyography, axiography, digital occlusal analysis (T-Scan), cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) provide more accurate detection of both functional and morphological changes in the TMJ area.

119. 4. Multimodal treatment strategies that combine occlusal correction, splint therapy, physiotherapeutic methods and psychosocial support demonstrate clinically significant improvement in most patients with TMJ dysfunction associated with occlusal interferences.

120. 5. Further development of approaches to the diagnosis and treatment of TMJ dysfunction requires unification of diagnostic criteria (in particular DC/TMD and RDC/TMD), harmonization of treatment protocols and wider implementation of digital technologies to ensure objective assessment and enhance the effectiveness of therapy.

121. Prospects for further research

122. Future studies should focus on conducting prospective randomized clinical trials evaluating the effectiveness of various strategies of occlusal correction in patients with TMJ dysfunction associated with occlusal interferences.

123. A promising direction is the integration of digital technologies (T-Scan, 3D modeling, navigation systems) into treatment planning and monitoring, as well as investigation of the role of inflammatory and remodeling biomarkers of joint structures for predicting disease course and personalizing therapy.

124. The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

125. Funding: The study received no external funding.

126. REFERENCES

127. 1. Trehan M, Sharma P, Tiwari A, Kumar A, Anamika, Bamal R. Prevalence of Temporomandibular Disorders in Young Adults and Their Association with Functional and Static Occlusal Parameters: A Cross-Sectional Study.

128. 2. Pascu L, Haiduc RS, Almășan O, Leucuța DC. Occlusion and Temporomandibular Disorders: A Scoping Review. *Medicina (Kaunas)*. 2025;61(5):791. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina61050791>.
129. 3. Okeson JP. Management of temporomandibular disorders and occlusion. 9th ed. Elsevier; 2023.
130. 4. De Leeuw R, Klasser GD. Orofacial pain: guidelines for assessment, diagnosis, and management. Batavia: Quintessence publishing; 2018. 30 p.
131. 5. Sharif M, Amjad A, Hussain S. Temporomandibular disorders in patients with occlusal interferences. *Pakistan Armed Forces Medical Journal*. 2022;72(6):2071-2073. <https://doi.org/10.51253/pafmj.v72i6.8001>
132. 6. Lekaviciute R, Kriauciunas A. Relationship Between Occlusal Factors and Temporomandibular Disorders: A Systematic Literature Review. *Cureus*. 2024;16(2):e54130. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.54130>.
133. 7. Singh BP, Singh N, Jayaraman S, Kirubakaran R, Joseph S, Muthu MS, et al. Occlusal interventions for managing temporomandibular disorders. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2024;9(9):CD012850. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/14651858.CD012850.pub2>. PMID: 39282765; PMCID: PMC11403706.
134. 8. Page M. J., McKenzie J. E., Bossuyt P. M., Boutron I., Hoffmann T. C., Mulrow C. D. et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement. *British Medical Journal*. 2021;372: n71. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>
135. 9. Ohrbach R, Dworkin SF. The evolution of DC/TMD Diagnosis: Past, Present, Future. *Journal of Oral Rehabilitation*. 2016;43(9):739-744. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022034516653922>.
136. 10. Kadekuzhi S, Karuveetil V, Prabha RD, Vallikat Velath A, N K SV, Ghosh P. et al. Morphological changes in temporomandibular joint architecture in patients with temporomandibular disorders: systematic review protocol. *BMJ Open*. 2024;14(9):e082396. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2023-082396>.

- 137.** 11. Gauer RL, Semidey MJ. Diagnosis and treatment of temporomandibular disorders. *American Family Physician*. 2015;91(6):378-386.
- 138.** 12. Oudkerk J, Grenade C, Davarpanah A, Vanheusden A, Vandenput S, Mainjot AK. Risk factors of tooth wear in permanent dentition: A scoping review. *Journal Oral Rehabilitation*. 2023;50(10):1110-1165. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joor.13489>.
- 139.** 13. Liu Y, Zheng Y, Long Y, Ye C, Zhang Q, Zhou X, Xiong X, Wang J. Cephalometric analysis of the relationship between temporomandibular joint disc displacement and occlusal plane. *BMC Oral Health*. 2025;25(1):1955. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-025-07015-w>.
- 140.** 14. Cardoneanu A, Macovei LA, Burlui AM, Mihai IR, Bratoiu I, Rezus II. et al. Temporomandibular Joint Osteoarthritis: Pathogenic Mechanisms Involving the Cartilage and Subchondral Bone, and Potential Therapeutic Strategies for Joint Regeneration. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2022;24(1):171. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24010171>.
- 141.** 15. Dygas S, Szarmach I, Radej I. Assessment of the Morphology and Degenerative Changes in the Temporomandibular Joint Using CBCT according to the Orthodontic Approach: A Scoping Review. *Biomed Res Int*. 2022;2022:6863014. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/6863014>.
- 142.** 16. Loan HK, Anh NTV, Duy TV, Hoa NT, Chien DQ, Au HD. Correlation Between Clicking Sound Symptoms and Magnetic Resonance Imaging Findings in Patients with Temporomandibular Joint Internal Derangement. *Med Arch*. 2025;9(2):155-158. <https://doi.org/10.5455/medarh.2025.79.155-158>.
- 143.** 17. Zhang R, Lai D, Zhang F, Qiao B, Chen J, Zhang Y. et al. A Comparative Analysis of Temporomandibular Disorders Using a Jaw Motion Analyzer and Surface Electromyography. *Int Dent J*. 2025;75(3):1843-1853. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.identj.2025.03.023>.
- 144.** 18. Choi BT, Hwang DY, Lee GH, Moon DN, Lee KM. Computerized ultrasonic axiographic evaluation of condylar movement in patients with internal derangement of the temporomandibular joint. *Angle Orthod*.

- 2019;89(6):924-929. <https://doi.org/10.2319/110618-792.1>.
- 145.** 19. Wojciechowska B, Szarmach A, Michcik A, Sikora M, Drogoszewska B. Is Ultrasonography an Effective Method for Diagnosing Degenerative Changes in the Temporomandibular Joint? *Biomedicines*. 2024;12(12):2915. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomedicines12122915>.
- 146.** 20. Cifter ED. Effects of Occlusal Plane Inclination on the Temporomandibular Joint Stress Distribution: A Three-Dimensional Finite Element Analysis. *Int J Clin Pract*. 2022;2022:2171049. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/2171049>.
- 147.** 21. Lile IE, Hajaj T, Constantin GD, Niculescu ST, Marian D, Stana O. et al. Association Between Occlusal Interferences, Temporomandibular Joint Dysfunction, and Bruxism in Romanian Adults. *J Clin Med*. 2025;14(16):5612. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm14165612>.
- 148.** 22. Bachani T, Raza FB, Vaidyanathan AK. The synergism of occlusal splints along with therapeutic exercise on individuals with temporomandibular joint disorders - A pilot study. *J Indian Prosthodont Soc*. 2025;25(1):52-58. https://doi.org/10.4103/jips.jips_373_24.
- 149.** 23. Moxley B, Stevens W, Sneed J, Pearl C. Novel Diagnostic and Therapeutic Approaches to Temporomandibular Dysfunction: A Narrative Review. *Life (Basel)*. 2023;13(9):1808. <https://doi.org/10.3390/life13091808>.
- 150.** 24. Chęciński M, Chęcińska K, Turosz N, Sikora M, Chlubek D. Intra-Articular Injections into the Inferior versus Superior Compartment of the Temporomandibular Joint: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *J Clin Med*. 2023;12(4):1664. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm12041664>.
- 151.** 25. Cezairli B, Halat İB, Balaban E. Evaluation of the correlation between articular disc displacement and the lateral pterygoid muscle using magnetic resonance imaging. *BMC Oral Health*. 2025;25(1):1733. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12903-025-07137-1>.
- 152.** 26. Kumar Maurya R, Singh H, Talwar B, Sharma P, Kapoor P. Biometric Assessment of Temporomandibular Disorders in Orthodontics: A Multi-arm Randomized Controlled Trial. *Turkish Journal of Orthodontics*.

2022;35(4):290-306. <https://doi.org/10.5152/TurkJOrthod.2022.21116>.

- 153.** 27. Dąbkowska I, Sobiech L, Czepińska A, Bęben A, Turzańska K, Gawda P. Multimodal Approaches in the Management of Temporomandibular Disorders: A Narrative Review. *J Clin Med.* 2025;14(12):4326. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcm14124326>.
- 154.** 28. Nykänen L, Sipilä K, Eli I, Freidman-Rubin P, Keren L, Kämppe A. et al. Brief Diagnostic Criteria for Temporomandibular Disorders: Sensitivity and Specificity of Clinical Diagnoses (A Multi-Center Study). *J Oral Rehabil.* 2025;52(8):1251-1258. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joor.13969>.
- 155.** 29. Maheshwari K, Srinivasan R, Singh BP, Tiwari B, Kirubakaran R. Effectiveness of anterior repositioning splint versus other occlusal splints in the management of temporomandibular joint disc displacement with reduction: A meta-analysis. *J Indian Prosthodont Soc.* 2024;24(1):15-24. https://doi.org/10.4103/jips.jips_355_23.
- 156.** 30. Manfredini D. Current concepts on temporomandibular disorders. Cham: Springer; 2021.
- 157.** 31. Belikov OB, Roshchuk OI, Belikova NI, Sorokhan MM, Karavan YaR. Modern views on the development of temporomandibular joint dysfunction associated with occlusal interferences: A systematic review. *Bulletin of problems in biology and medicine* 2025;4 (179):7-18 <https://doi.org/10.29254/2077-4214-2025-4-179-7-18>
- 158.** This manuscript is a preprint and has not been peer-reviewed. It is intended for early dissemination of research results. Citation of this work should consider its preprint nature.